

THEORETICAL BASIS OF USING DIDACTIC GAMES IN THE PROCESS OF MOTHER TONGUE EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article analyzes the theoretical basis of using didactic games in the process of mother tongue education based on specific sources.

Key words: Game, simplifying, complicating, teacher, self-thinking, learned topics, accounting, training content, indicators, looking at structure, grammar, effect, organization, positive influence, etc.

INTRODUCTION: The organization of didactic games also requires taking into account a number of methodological factors. Applying this method to the teaching process, the teacher needs to approach each subject and its content creatively. Another important aspect is that the characteristics of the students of the class should be taken into account when organizing grammar games. Taking into account the students' level of mastery, which class they study in, and the topics studied, and the content of the training based on these indicators. Structuring has a positive effect on the effective organization of grammar games. It allows for quick and solid mastering of learned grammatical concepts. Regardless of which section of grammar the grammar games are conducted, they should not be accidental. The teacher should prepare for him as carefully as he prepares for the lesson.

REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE: Children should be ready for any grammar game. It does not develop the condition. It distracts the child. If the game is started several times, such an activity becomes boring and ultimately affects the child's cognitive activity. In order to prevent it, the content of each assigned assignment should be fully explained, similar examples should be performed, and an example should be given. Grammatically possible. This is determined by the teacher himself. Games for children can be complicated or simplified depending on the level of knowledge of children. The game becomes more complicated. When the game of creating a sentence with the given words is played, the game becomes simpler if the work is shown starting from the word. The teacher himself thinks about simplifying or complicating the game it is necessary. It is necessary not to be limited to the active participation of one or two children in the game. Most of the students, if possible, should actively participate in it. Because the game educates children in the community spirit. When children play games as a team, the intended goal can be achieved only when all its members actively participate. In this exercise, all students

work towards the same goal. Everyone strives to be a winner. This situation increases the responsibility of each student. The student answering tries to justify the trust of his group. If he gives the wrong answer, he feels uncomfortable in front of the children, and in some cases, he gets angry. He will carefully prepare for the next matches. Such activities encourage children to study more. The desire to win encourages people to come together. Someone loses in the game. This is natural. Therefore, game competitions teach children another quality, to admit defeat. This is very important in child education. Sometimes students have their own they don't admit their defeat, they try to find fault with someone, they accuse the referees of being "sold out".

Such events often occur in school life. In this case, you should not get bored of explaining to the student. After one or two such discussions, you should not stop the games. Development of school education State In the third direction of the Decree on the national program on the improvement of educational standards, curriculum and textbooks, improved versions of DTS, programs, textbooks have been prepared and work is being carried out on the basis of them. standard was prepared. According to him: the acquired knowledge of grammar; - phonetics, morphology, syntax and lexicology, word structure, word formation, writing and spelling, speech styles, methodological concepts.

development of speech: - the first direction - development of students' vocabulary; - the second direction - to teach the standards of the Uzbek literary language, to introduce the standards of literary pronunciation, as well as dictionary synonymy, adverbial synonymy, and grammatical synonymy in general; - the third direction - it is necessary to develop the ability and skills of students to express their thoughts verbally and in writing. Based on this, the main goal of mother tongue education: It is necessary to focus on the formation and development of the skills of creativity, independent thinking, and the ability to express the product of creative thought in oral and written forms in accordance with the speech conditions. At this time, the importance of native language textbooks is important in performing this complex and responsible task.

Educational tasks that serve to develop students' creative thinking are given in Uzbek language textbooks of secondary schools. These assignments should be completed independently by the students in cooperation with the teacher in various ways. One of the main types of assignments that give positive results are grammar games-tasks. Games-tasks are very important in the interesting passage of mother tongue lessons. However, grammar games-tasks and the methodology of their use are not developed enough in "Methodology of Uzbek language teaching". The advantage of this is that

it is often organized as a competition. As a result, giving incentives or points to students and groups will undoubtedly increase students' motivation to complete the task. As a result, students' grammatical literacy, the ability to think creatively, ingenuity, speech and love for this subject will increase significantly. At the same time, the use of additional literature creates the need to seriously engage in other subjects. It is advisable to make good use of various games-assignments and puzzles in order to learn. Today's demand also requires skill, creativity, and most importantly, tireless work from the teacher of science. Taking this into account, it is possible to use it when passing mother tongue lessons. Let's look at some grammar games, puzzles and methods of using them. It is possible to invent many more such grammar games and use them in the course of the lesson. This, as mentioned above, depends on the creativity, inquisitiveness, skill and tireless work of the teacher. It is known that the games and tasks are grouped according to the level of complexity according to the qualifications and skills of the students, from simple to complex dynamics.

Memorization-type game tasks. Such game-tasks are more often used in lessons to strengthen the learned topics and to test knowledge and skills. For example, in order to reinforce lessons on the topic of "Famous and Kindred Horses", "Who is the winner?" it is appropriate to use a game-task. For this, the class is divided into two groups: one will find examples of common nouns, and the other will find examples of related nouns. The teacher writes the words diary, photo, movie, book, newspaper, magazine, on the board separately. The class is divided into six groups (the number of students must be taken into account. can decrease or increase the number), they are required to write examples of these nouns. Each member of the group writes one example of the word related to him. The winners must be encouraged. Such games can be used to reinforce the desired topic. can be conducted. In this, students are given basic words and phrases (they can also be written on the board) and are instructed to use them to create a connected text. The student who writes a quick and meaningful text is the winner. is counted. Increasing the vocabulary of students is one of the requirements of DTS, it is good to use game-tasks of the nature of inquiry, which gives a good result for the development of this skill. Such tasks require students to be creative. "Creative" o The game-task can be effectively used to pass the topic "Ravish". In this grammar game, the class is divided into two groups, and the first group is given examples of sentences with adjectives, and the second group is given the noun(s) in these sentences. is assigned to make a sentence by replacing it. For example: The representative of the first group writes: I wrote a good essay (what kind of essay?) in the Olympiad. The second group continues: Our group will

participate well in it (how did it participate?). It will be continued in this way. It is also possible to continue this game between students or between parallel classes in the form of "word exchange". In the process of learning the mother tongue, language phenomena are observed by means of the task system. they are compared, similar and different aspects are determined, they are grouped according to their general and specific aspects, general rules are formed. As a result, there is a dynamic growth from recollection tasks to creative tasks. Such tasks are of particular importance in the development of the student's thinking. Determining and defining the dynamics of the growth of educational tasks from simple to complex is a complex process. it should have a positive effect on the development of the student's thinking. Creative tasks, that is, tasks that develop the student's thinking, should have their own characteristics: let him find; - it is necessary to direct the student to draw an independent conclusion; - as the problem becomes more complicated, the student should be smart and develop his insight; - the course of this process should develop students' teamwork skills; - the process of completing tasks must encourage the student to gain self-confidence, self-awareness (knowledge), ability to identify opportunities, and to acquire new knowledge. In the textbooks created on the basis of the updated educational content, in the classes for all departments of linguistics, the lessons begin with the analysis of assignments for each subject without starting with definitions and rules, that is, without giving knowledge to students ready-made. This is where the teacher's skills, abilities, and learning are manifested. It is in this process that he gradually moves from one method of activity to another method of activity, that is, from observation to grouping based on common characteristics, from repetition to the similarities and differences. generalizations are formed on the basis of identification. Only then the tasks given serve to reveal the nature of language phenomena. In the 5th grade, the following grammatical tasks can be used during the phonetics section: task 1. Make different words with i-u, a-o, o'-u, i-e, b-p, d-t, z-s, j-ch pairs. Assignment. Create pairs of words that differ in x-h sounds. Pay attention to the pronunciation of the phoneme H. Task. Find words for the letter combination ng and divide them into syllables.

Task. Find the similarities and differences between the words "Good" and "Bad". Similarities: 5 letters, 2 vowels, 3 consonants, 2 syllables, the accent falls on the end, 5 sounds. What's the difference? What is its meaning? What is its antonym?

Assignment. Create a chain of words with the sound "x". Happiness - throne - egg - mirrih - imagination - lakhtak - kimhob - velvet - clot - axta - akhir - permission - board - morals - qix - sad - akhir - permission - throne - takhlit - guess - price - message - permission - axtar - rukhsor. The game serves as a functional entry into

the world of childhood and mediation is important in the formation of the child's personality and the construction of all aspects of movement, social, mental and cognitive. Through various game activities, the child forms, recognizes colors and sizes and relies on things that distinguish the surrounding things, their relationships and functions and significance, and this enriches his mental knowledge with various forms of information about the world. Considering the importance of thinking in human life, modern educational trends are aimed at revising the curriculum and training students at all levels of education, which enable students to practice different thinking skills. creates many opportunities for. Therefore, the development of thinking skills in children is one of the main directions of preparing kindergarten programs for children. [6]. "Thinking skills are important skills in a child's life, so the educational literature emphasizes the benefits of using fun and enjoyable play to recruit these skills" (El-Nashef, 1996).

The results of many studies emphasize the effectiveness of games in child education, for example, Abdel Ghani (1996), Goldholer et al. thus aimed at developing his thinking skills and using modern educational methods. 1 When planning games for primary school students, the following should be taken into account:

starting with simple play, children learn best through familiar experiences;

educational games should be at the level of knowledge of children;

c) educational games should be lively and related to attention, should increase interest;

created in simple language and understood by the child.

related to the child's needs, inclinations and desire to explore the world around him.

CONCLUSION: In addition to the above, the games designed for children in primary grades should be closely related to the reality of his life, and should also provide him with intuition and consciousness and interrelated should provide an opportunity to identify concrete examples that can be easily felt from the environment [16]. can plan their games.

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